

Factors Affecting Students Learning and Behavior

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Abstract:

The study deals with the problems and difficulties that are faced by students in the classroom especially the Learning and Behavior issues that are often witnessed. There are certain factors that lead to these learning and behavior problems which include parent or teacher attitude, disabilities and many others which this paper will discuss in depth. Students face a myriad of problems and issues that impact the psychologically and sociologically and that further integrate into their learning and grasping in the classroom. On the flip side the classroom can also become a hostile place for learners of all ages due to clashes and attitudes of the teachers. In turn there are many other complicating factors that can deter the learning curve and throw a negative light on students' behavior in the classroom. These factors affect student behavior throughout the spectrum; from early learning till tertiary education. These are triggers that will affect a student throughout their educational profile.

Keywords: Classroom, Teachers, Behavior, Parents, Psychological Barriers, Language Barriers

Introduction

Behavior is specified as the way one shows or organizes oneself in a public or private manner but, particularly towards others. It is repeatedly a response to a particular position or impetus. Behavior has influence on each and every aspect of life. It is imperative to say that the behaviors are closely related to the situations and surroundings and its impact can create the positive or negative effects on the personality of an individual (Smelser et al., 2020).

This study examines the factors which are the cause of the students' problematic behavior and these factors affect the behavior and learning abilities of the students. Students discover actions and through the criticism and concerns that they regularly have at home or school. Sometimes response or concerns accidentally strengthen adverse behavior because parents and teachers are not careful of their words or actions. For instance, a teacher reacts to a student who often asks out in class by providing him more interest, and kind of forgets the others; which is what he wants. Or students that are then labeled as trouble makers try to find sent out of class for interrupting the class in order to avoid a task or pursuit they hate. And this is then reinforced in their habits regularly (Smelser et al., 2020).

To efficiently support students with performance in capacities and to help them create new and more optimistic behaviors, teachers should realize why students behave as they do. One effective way of understanding students' problem behavior is to understand that the behavior has a role. In many cases, the performance lets students to find something they want or avoid something they choose or prevent something they do not want (Sequeira, 2021).

Home Environment

As we know that from the beginning the environment & domestic issues have been a huge impact on the grooming of the child with respect to the academic and cognitive point of view as they have been remaining an important element. Many practices have shown that the house environment parameters can be divided into 2 main parts public and private (Casey, Bradley, Nelson & Whaley, 1988; Wachs, 1989).

As we know by experience and by the knowledge that the first social unit will be house as it has been since the start of the day. Moreover, one family's living style or connections has an impact on the children as they will learn what they will see and seek from their home environment or from their institute. Both of these help the students to grow, learn new things also in their maturity grooming and discipline, etc. However, in this modern era still, the factors did not change, and neither will they change. Besides home life, there are so many other issues like personal intelligence, disabilities, teacher's attitude, etc (Jayson & Sharon, 2008)

Parent's Relationship with Their Children

The environment of the house in which a little one is reared can amplify or ward off healthy private adjustment. Family relationships additionally determine in the big measure the more youthful man or woman's developing attitudes in the route of home and family life. Basically, the effects of the most important factors on behavior, joy, and on temper are one's own family or relatives' circle in which they are growing. If the temper in the family is harsh then it will affect badly on their child and will cause the bad performance of the student in the classroom because all the angry thoughts will be recirculated in his mind (McMillan & Hiltonsmith, 1982).

One should understand that as much the house environment maintained by parents will be goodwill consequence in healthier performance of their kid in the classroom who grow in happy houses in which young humans and the parents are spending more time together not only because to make their relationship better but also because of the need of the hour to provide a better environment to their child and when the student mind is fresh and healthy than he will be able to get good performance in the classroom (Noller & Victor, 1991).

Mother and father are typically pondered in a warm and supportive circle of relatives climate. The war between the dad and mom is probably to result in a normal as the environment is not good than the students' performance will not be good moreover the bad environment of the house created by the family will also affect the student's moral behavior and manners. Moreover, the students will start to face emotional and sensitive problems with them and it's very difficult for one to get over these situations, most of the students have ruined their careers because of these issues. A person's dad and mom determine, in detail, an own family's method of infant rearing. In reality, numerous many years of exploration guide the ongoing lifestyles of important aspects of parent conduct (Camp, 2011).

The primary, recognition-rejection, specializes in the consequences of parent conduct that is either hot or aggressive. A warmth courting permits kids to be responsible and self-controlled, at the same time as hostility has a tendency to sell aggression. The second length, manipulate autonomy, specializes in how limiting or lenient dad and mom are in imposing regulations of performance. Mothers and fathers who use strict management usually have youngsters who're well-behaved however especially set up. People who are permissive usually will definitely have children who have high in anger and social ability. One must say that no other approach is most beneficial than this one or can more explain the situation than this one examined by practices (Fabes & Lynn, 2000).

Authoritarian child rearing: this kind of national is created by fathers who know that each and every action will be effected on their children so they will try their best to make the house environment as good as they can, which will result in overall good performance of their child also in academic activities too, with rigid standards of conduct. Those parents usually respect subservience and choice cruel, vigorous actions, collectively with bodily penance, to guarantee that kids take a look at their regulations. The parents discourage verbal provide and-take, believing that youngsters want to take delivery of their phrase for what's proper. Therefore, the authoritarian mother and father are immoderate in demanding their responsiveness. That mothers and fathers set guidelines and count on that youngster (Baumrind 1971; Kochanska & Askan, 1995).

Permissive Parenting

As the research and deep study have shown that those parents who do not demand and desires a lot from their children are such a kind of parents who already accepted the desires of their children no matter what they are, just for the sake to make their affection connection better. The one's dad and mom view themselves as property to be used as their children desire in preference to as dealers answerable because to have to be able for

determining & shifting their youngster's morale. As we know that the type of permissive parents can't put pressure on their children which will not disturb them will result in no dream completion or success of their child in academic performance or in daily life (Acker & Davis, 1992).

Uninvolved Parenting

As we know that this type of parent is those who have no more demands from their children and remain in their own comfort zone. But the studies have shown that this type of behavior is less responsive in this case the children will not try hard to achieve something and will cause less output in their curricular and extracurricular activities. The parents should give more impotence to their children ethic and mental development instead of not saying a single word or require no demand from them. These things will make them lazy and ignore them from their determination. So the parents should support their children and involve themselves in their children grooming which will result in the student's educational improvement too (Breiner, Ford, & Gadsden, 2016).

Deprived Socioeconomic Environment

Culturally Deprived

This term is used rather than "culturally different" because of the fact that children coming from other cultural contexts are often handicapped in adjustment to the school. The use of the term is not meant to imply the superiority of one culture over another in any sense except preparation for school as it is presently structured (Saville, 1978).

The educational disadvantages suffered by children from deprived socioeconomic environments have been a source of concern to educators for some time. Children who come to school without the background necessary to profit from school experiences encounter repeated frustrations as they attempt to adapt to the new and strange environment. The result of such frustrations, in all too many cases, is that they reject the entire school situation, along with the values it represents, and seek satisfaction in other pursuits, some of which are often detrimental to themselves and to the community (Ferguson, Bovaird, & Mueller, 2007).

To make matters even worse, they become the parents of children who will experience similar frustrations and lack of need-satisfaction in their encounters with the middle-class-oriented school, thus establishing a cycle of failure and rejection. Concern over this state of affairs has been heightened and focused by federal actions designed to aid the culturally deprived child in his adjustment to school. In particular, Project Head start was designed to perform this function for the kindergarten-age child through programs intended to supplement his experiential background in areas necessary for school success (Mulford, 2003).

A real problem arose in connection with these efforts when it was found that objective criteria for determining the degree and type of deprivation had not been developed. For want of a better measure, the level of family income has been used as a prime criterion in the selection of children for the first Head start programs. However, the inadequacy of such a criterion has been clearly pointed out by others, who have correctly noted that this particular variable is only one of many which are related to the problem (Havighurst, 1964).

Other variables may have as much or more pertinence to the problem of identifying children in need of supplementary experience to prepare them. For school are such matters as self-concepts, attitudes, values, knowledge, and understanding of relationships and familiarity with objects or names of objects encountered in the typical school experience (Ornstein, 1966).

At the present time, however, there is considerable uncertainty about the precise relationship between many of these variables and school success because of the lack of instruments and procedures for their assessment, especially on the kindergarten degree. The primary purpose of this project was to derive and make preliminary trials of some procedures by which the assessment of variables such as those listed above might be accomplished at the kindergarten level (Ornstein, 1966).

Physical Disabilities

One of the most critical aspects in student behavior is physical handicap and differently unable obstacles in learning. Educators make a concerted effort to provide specific supports for kids with impairments' academic achievements. Involvement with unable classmates, on the other hand, is commonly thought to be a strategy to

support these kids' social participation, especially if their main disabling condition is not social conduct (Stein, Westbrook & Silver, 1998).

Recent studies representative that early people with long-lasting illnesses and impairments have a higher likelihood of alteration difficulties and developing difficult common skills has elevated fundamental queries regarding the basis for this supposition (Lavigne & Routman, 1992). Children with essential physical disabilities made up a large majority of the participants in this study; yet, few studies have looked into whether these pupils had more difficulties reaching the social and behavioral requirements of the school program (Stein, Westbrook & Silver, 1998).

Learning/Psychological/Physical Challenges

Both physical and psychological challenges can prevent students from learning well in the classroom. Many schools have doctors and therapists that help identify and manage these special needs children before the problem exasperates itself (Laar et al., 2021).

Learning Disabilities

Students with learning difficulties are another factor that affects student behaviour. Many teachers believe that students with learning disabilities should be incorporated as seamlessly as possible into regular classrooms. Pupils with education infirmities are sometimes described the same as "inactive learners" in elementary and secondary schools, lingering on the perimeter of academic and social participation (Torgeson, 1982).

As stated in the case for integration, isolating these kids from their peers without impairments makes them even more dysfunctional, such as a consequence, students with in capacities must restore themselves as ordinary members on a regular basis. Some educators must spoke out against the separating consequences of removing pupils from general education classrooms, arguing that the only way to achieve effective integration is for general and special education to be restructured holistically (Gartner & Lipsky, 1987; Reynolds, Wang, & Walberg, 1987).

Others need suggest that before approving such organization, a thorough examination of general education practices with kids with disabilities be conducted (Braaten, Kauffman, Braaten, Polsgrove & Nelson, 1988; McKinney & Hocutt, 1988; Mesigner, 1985). Pupils with Understanding In-capacities (LD) are identified by academic tasks, mainly in learning, prose, and/or math (also known as Specific Learning Difficulties or Specific Learning Disorders) (American Psychiatric Association, 2013).

As a result, the conventional focus of involvement for these pupils have been on the construction of successful learning courses, with a focus on learning, prose, and count, and bit interest made to emotive and social factors. Adolescents with LD, on the other hand, face challenges at school that go beyond learning skills like interest and remembrance. Several findings have looked at a amount of problems associated to the passionate and public phases of education for kids with LD .Agreeing to the DSM-5, "specific learning disorders can have severe functional ramifications across the lifespan," such as "high levels of psychological distress and poorer overall mental health" (American Psychiatric Association, 2013). Falling out of school but experiencing depressive indicators increases the risk of bad emotional physical condition outcomes (Butler & Silliman, 2008; Elias, 2004; Schiff & Joshi, 2016).

Kids who are fewer popular among their classmates have got less chances to relate and form relationships, and they are more likely to suffer frequent feelings of isolation, resulting in bad prosocial behaviour and disturbing grief (Mugnaini, Lassi, Malfa & Albertini, 2009; Pearl, 1998). Positive peer interactions, on the other hand, lead to improved emotional change (Bagwell, Newcomb, & Bukowski, 1998; Schneider, Wiener, & Murphy, 1994).Classroom isolation, difficulties dealing with university duties, and recurring experiences of university fiasco have all been shown to have a negative influence on kids with LD self-efficacy and self-esteem (Zelege, 2004).

Researchers found that kids with LD contrast their acting to that of their friends and identify themselves as unique, fewer appreciated, and fewer brilliant. Irritation, nervousness, and frustration are commonly associated to breakdowns in school hopes such as reading aloud in front of colleagues or conditions in which conventional

training methods depend on merely on writing-reading abilities. Such situations have a bad influence on the purpose and participation of students with LD in the school room (Gadeyne, Ghesquière, & Onghena, 2004; Humphrey & Mullins, 2002).

Several studies have found that universal social-emotional learning programme improve social, emotional, and academic outcomes, including a decrease in aggressive, anti-social, and conduct behaviors, as well as emotional distress, depressive symptoms and risk-behaviors (Horowitz & Garber, 2007).

Strategies have played an important role on positive attitudes toward oneself, and also towards others, and learning, as well as helps in academic accomplishment, according to meta-analyses and reviews of evaluative studies (Catalano, Berglund, Ryan, Lonczak, & Hawkins, 2002; Sklad, Diekstra, Ritter, & Ben, 2012; Taylor, Oberle, Durlak, & Weissberg, 2017).

A learning disability is thought to be a neurological disorder affecting the brain's ability to receive, analyze, store, and respond to data (National Research Center for Learning Disabilities, 2007). The term "learning disability" refers to a person of average intelligence's inability to learn basic academic and functional skills. A person's ability to grasp and use spoken and written language, execute mathematical computations, coordinate motions, or focus their attention can all be hampered by learning issues. The National Research Center for Learning Disabilities (NRCLD) published a report in 2007.

Reading is the most difficult field for those children who have learning difficulties (LD). Children with reading difficulties often battle with spelling and reading, which is usually the result of a descriptive linguistics processing problem. They can also face problem remembering words they've already memorized (Ehri & McCormick, 1998). Other signs of a reading problem include difficulty apprehension of the words (Gersten, Fuchs, Williams, & Baker, 2001).

Problems with oral and written communication, such as talking, listening, reading and all the fields which are related to reading are examples of language-related learning difficulties. Dysgraphia indicates the difficulties in writing, formation of letters or words or writing within a limited space, and it is a type of learning disability which is closely related to writing. Memorizing the spelling and its grammatical structures, create information, putting imagination on paper are some of the other learning disorders associated to written work (Berninger, 2009). Dyscalculia is a term used to describe math-related learning problems (Shaley, Manor, & Tsur, 2005).

Dyscalculia is a condition in which people face problem to understand mathematical concepts and computations, often even with very easy math sums. Problems with sequencing, and other problems like time and direction are all examples of math impairments. The people who have difficulty in understanding the math problems, also find reading difficulty in some people, but math inability are more directly tied to problems with working remembering and thought process in others (Swanson, 2009).

Self-perspective deficits, interpersonal skills deficits, focusing difficulties, memorization problems, and motor skills deficits are among the additional attribute discovered by this study (Mather & Goldstein, 2008). When we observe gender inequalities in students with learning difficulties, male students need more special education assistance as compared to female students. Male students are diagnosed with learning disabilities 2 to 6 times more often than female students (Smith, 1994). Furthermore, according to Vogel, "female students with LD have more problems in maths and in reading, but male students have more difficulty in visual-motor abilities, spelling, and formation of language mechanism than females". However, if we don't consider gender, the most of the students with LD display problematic demeanor (Vogel, 1990).

As previously stated, early detection of problems increases the likelihood of successful intervention attempts. Early identification refers to spotting difficulties in young children as well as spotting early symptoms of troublesome conduct. Early symptoms of prospective learning impairments and behavioral abnormalities, according to several researchers, can be consistently detected (Dunlap, 2006; Feil, 2005). Furthermore, studies have indicated that the sooner LD is recognized and care begins, the higher the possibility of avoiding school failure and improving life opportunities.

Learning challenges usually emerge throughout the elementary school years, as these disabilities are fail to fulfill the challenging and refined learning project. The mentors and parents should seek investigation if they feel their child has learning problems (Matthew & Goldstein, 2008).

Classroom Environment

Students with behavioral and emotional issues frequently respond in an inconsistent manner to instructor demands and engage in troubled attitudes in the classroom. In 2008, Conroy, Sutherland, Snyder, and Marsh published a paper on what are the factors which can effect classroom environment on students' learning. Although teachers prefer to give punishments when it comes to manage the class disciplined, many classrooms environments are not conducive to learning for students (Conroy, Sutherland, Snyder, & Marsh, 2008). Most teachers, according to Westling (2010), do not apply appropriate classroom management tactics, and challenging student conduct has a detrimental impact on the entire classroom atmosphere and subsequent relationships between students and teachers. Teachers can make strategies and adopt latest methodologies in the classroom to encourage interactive and can decrease behavior issues (Conroy, Sutherland, Snyder, & Marsh, 2008).

In order to avoid these problematic issues in classroom conduct, teachers must first identify behavior issues. If teachers identify that what is the reason for the student's disruptive behavior, the teacher may look for the strategies to regroup the class environment to overcome the problems which students are facing in classrooms. Students with behavioral and emotional issues frequently respond in an inconsistent manner to instructor demands (Banks, 2014). In a 2004 research survey, 75% of teachers gave their opinions that due to these disruptive behaviors, they spend less time in teaching and in enhancing their teaching methodologies and they spend more time in dealing behavior problems (Public Agenda, 2004).

Teachers should make strategies to provide interactive learning environments and be able to maintain and control classroom conditions that can be helpful in attaining the desired behavior (Hardman & Smith, 1999). Teachers who make caring surroundings anticipate potential challenges, establish rules and consequences, focus classroom supports on positive behavior, guide them rather than using the tool of reprimand for behavior change, and provide students with the freedom to achieve their goal.(Hardman & Smith, 1999).

Teachers, who succeed in providing pleasant classroom environments, have great knowledge about the environmental factors in their classroom environment. Poor and in-disciplined classroom structure is frequently the cause of these rowdy behavior problems. The organized classroom environment can affect students' conduct, that doesn't require teacher intervention, but careful thought process of how the environment is organized might be helpful. Problematic behavior prevention is an important aspect of classroom behavior management. As a result, preceding stimulation and preventative methods are necessary factors of a comprehensive classroom management programs (Smith & Misr, 1992).

The connection between the student behavior, classroom atmosphere and academic participation has been studied by researchers (Hood-Smith & Leffingwell, 1983; Visser, 2001). A well-organized classroom promotes more interaction with students, reduces the probability of problematic behavior (Martella. Nelson, & Martella, 2003). Changing the classroom surroundings can also be used as a direct engagement for children who display persistent troubled demeanor (Conroy, Davis, Fox, & Brown, 2002).

The importance of a well-designed classroom have been proved, there is limited study that environment plays a pivotal role on behavior and learning (Guardino, 2009; Schilling & Schwartz, 2004).Disciplined environment is the best and whole-class approach that can assist kids with prolonged behavior problems and facilitate children with limited problem behavior to acquire learning without interruption. Many teachers are unaware that the environmental changes are the important feature of classroom management (Emmer & Stough, 2001).

The instructor should first watch the children in the classroom, and identify the reason behind this disruptive behavior, as well as how different areas of the classroom are used. Are students, for example, unable to work without being distracted by their friends? Are students making trouble in the class as the material are disorganized and difficult to find? Following the observation, the teacher should consider what choices are available for improving problem areas in the classroom. • Arranging classroom furniture to delineate learning spaces , improving the availability of the material, improving the organized material (Buard, 2010; Guardino, 2008; Lawry, Danko, & Strain, 1999).

Teachers can use preventative tactics to improve optimistic student behavior and lessen disruptive behavior by identifying, planning, and implementing them. We discussed easy and practical ways that teachers can use to help students study in a happy environment (Oliver& Reschly, 2007).

Teacher Behavior Effects On Students Behavior

Teacher behavior in the classroom and with students is quite important, as the student will be able to develop excellent behavior if he learns it from his teachers. You could say that pupils will bow down to whatever their teachers sow into them. Because behavior is one of the most important aspects of any workplace, instructors should model good moral standards and strive to be supportive of their pupils so that they can learn more and achieve better academic results. The teacher's behavior has a significant impact on student behavior, such as self-esteem, discipline, satisfaction, students' performance, grooming, and social development (Oliver & Reschly, 2007).

A good teacher will always endeavor to improve his behavior toward his students, even if the student makes mistakes. If the mistakes are little and the instructor forgives him by providing him a good ethical lesson, the student will be encouraged and his or her confidence and behavior will improve. Furthermore, teachers should be aware of their pupils' talents and strive to improve them (Goodman, 2022).

Lack of Motivation

Lack of desire for academic activity is one of the most serious academic issues confronting today's teenagers. For unknown reasons, many high school students are continually distracted and demotivated and lack the drive to complete the academic activities that are needed of them (Green-Demers & Pelletier, 2003). Lack of academic motivation can produce irritation and dissatisfaction, as well as decreased productivity and well-being (Harackiewicz & Hidi, 2000).

The advantages of self-determined ordinance in the academic setting have been identified by large-scale studies on what encourages students in conducive learning classroom during the last two decades (Reeve, 2002; Vallerand, Fortier, & Guay, 1997; Vallerand, 1993).

Self-determination has been connected to a variety of good results, including increased psychological feature, abstract understanding, and active information physical process, as well as improved academic performance and academic self-concept (Deci, Vallerand, Pelletier, & Ryan, 1991; Reeve, Bolt, & Cai, 1999). Extrinsic motivation that is less self-determined has been connected to undesirable consequences such as sadness, egoism, bad impact, and physical illness (Deci & Ryan, 1985, 2002).

Conclusion

This research is important to focus the factors influencing student's problematic behavior. This study helps to identify the factors which create the deficiencies in student's behavior and helps the teachers to effectively support the students in coping with behavior disorders and help them to create positive environment for others also. This study benefits the teacher's need to understand why the students are facing difficulty in coping the daily task and how they create the strategies to overcome these deficiencies. Literature assessment indicates the same thing which we have discussed further that the fear and anger in the home will result in an effect of the educational psychology of the student. During the once several decades, home terrain has been linked as being a contributing thing in toddlers' academic enhancement. The home 6 surroundings and family procedure give a community of social and intellectual forces, which affect the scholars' literacy. Training consists of the effects designedly deliberate, chosen, and hired by way of the network for the weal of its coming generations. The cause is to modify the conduct of the child and to shape his persona in a suitable manner. This takes a look at a way of exploring the factors which affect the scholars' educational fulfillment and character development will help the speakers, directors, class itineraries, and policymakers to coordinate in an important manner so that our council scholars will have a licit character and advanced educational success after completing their formal education.

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